

Characterization of complex environmental contaminant mixtures in common toad breeding ponds in Flanders, Belgium

S. Devliegere^{a,*}, T. Goessens^{b,1}, S. De Baere^a, E. Blomme^{c,d}, A. Barbi^c, E. Meers^e, L. Vanhaecke^f, P. Spanoghe^g, A. Martel^c, F. Batsleer^d, D. Bonte^d, F. Pasmans^c, S. Croubels^a

^a Laboratory of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Ghent University, Salisburylaan 133, 9820, Merelbeke-Melle, Belgium

^b Centre of Excellence in Mycotoxicology and Public Health, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Ghent University, Ottergemsesteenweg 460, 9000, Ghent, Belgium

^c Wildlife Health Ghent, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Ghent University, Salisburylaan 133, 9820, Merelbeke-Melle, Belgium

^d Terrestrial Ecology Unit, Faculty of Sciences, Ghent University, Ledeganckstraat 35, 9000, Ghent, Belgium

^e Laboratory of Bioresource Recovery, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, Ghent University, Coupure Links 653, 9000, Ghent, Belgium

^f Laboratory of Integrative Metabolomics, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Ghent University, Salisburylaan 133, 9820, Merelbeke-Melle, Belgium

^g Laboratory of Crop Protection Chemistry, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, Ghent University, Coupure Links 653, 9000, Ghent, Belgium

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Environmental contaminants
Amphibians
Population decline
Multi-analyte analysis

ABSTRACT

The European common toad (*Bufo bufo*) is undergoing widespread population declines, potentially influenced by multiple environmental stressors, including chemical pollution. This study aimed to link the toad population status and contaminant levels in 20 breeding ponds in Flanders (Belgium). A multi-contaminant analytical approach was applied, using solid-phase extraction (SPE) combined with advanced instrumental methods: ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS/MS) for pesticides and mycotoxins, UHPLC-Orbitrap-high resolution MS for pharmaceuticals, inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) and ICP-MS for high and low-concentrated metals, respectively, and ion chromatography (IC) for nutrients. Across ponds, 25 pesticides, 11 mycotoxins, 13 antimicrobial drugs, 5 antiparasitic drugs, and 11 metals were detected, reaching concentrations up to 114 ng/L (pesticides), 88.2 ng/L (mycotoxins), 837 ng/L (antimicrobials), 26.8 ng/L (antiparasitic drugs), and 7382 µg/L (metals). Temporal variability was pronounced, with episodic increases in pesticide and metal levels, declining nitrate and sulphate concentrations, and increasing enniatin levels from March to June. Despite frequent co-contamination, no direct relationship was observed between individual contaminant levels and toad population status. These findings suggest that population declines are unlikely to be driven by a single substance, but rather by combined pressures associated with complex contaminant mixtures and other environmental stressors.

1. Introduction

Amphibians are currently the most threatened class of vertebrates worldwide, according to the IUCN Red List (Luedtke et al., 2023). Even widespread species, such as the European common toad (*Bufo bufo*), are experiencing gradual population declines (Petrovan et al., 2025). Like many amphibians, common toads have a complex life cycle encompassing both aquatic and terrestrial stages, making them integral components of both aquatic and terrestrial food webs (Fritz and Whiles, 2018). Conservation research is traditionally focused on rare or highly threatened species, while common species are often overlooked. Yet, even minor declines in abundant species can substantially reduce

ecosystem biomass and disrupt key functions, such as nutrient cycling between aquatic and terrestrial systems (Gaston and Fuller, 2008). Understanding the drivers of population declines in common amphibians is therefore critical for effective conservation strategies.

Population declines are generally driven by a complex interplay of multiple stressors, which can vary between species and life stages (Blaustein et al., 2011; Nolan et al., 2023). Amphibians are particularly vulnerable to infectious diseases, including bacterial, fungal, viral, protozoan, and mesomycetozoan pathogens. Among these, chytridiomycosis - caused by a chytrid fungus - remains one of the most significant threats, contributing to widespread declines (Martel et al., 2014; Stegen et al., 2017). Climate change further exacerbates

* Corresponding author.

¹ Shared first authorship.

population reductions, as evidenced by shifts in migration timing and reductions in body size linked to rising temperatures in common toads (Blomme et al., 2025; Reading and Jofré, 2021). Habitat loss and degradation from urbanization and agricultural intensification are among the most frequently reported threats, affecting genetic diversity, body condition, metamorphic timing, and behaviour, and ultimately increasing vulnerability to predation and environmental stress (Janin et al., 2011; Luedtke et al., 2023; Salazar et al., 2016). Importantly, these altered landscapes often coincide with increased exposure to environmental contaminants. Common toads, as habitat generalists widespread in agricultural landscapes, are particularly at risk, encountering pollutants throughout both aquatic and terrestrial life stages (Adams et al., 2021b; Berger et al., 2013, 2012; Churko et al., 2024; Lenhardt et al., 2015; Smalling et al., 2015; Taylor et al., 2024). Certain contaminants - including pesticides, veterinary drugs, mycotoxins, and metals - have been known to cause both mortality and sublethal effects such as impaired growth and development, deformities, and altered behaviour. In addition, nutrient inputs from agricultural runoff, such as nitrogen and phosphorus, can alter pond water chemistry and primary productivity, influencing food availability, larval growth, and overall amphibian population health (Mann et al., 2009). To date most of the toxicity studies have been conducted under laboratory conditions, focusing on individual contaminants, while the impact of complex environmental mixtures in natural settings remains largely unexplored (Albuquerque et al., 2024; Flynn et al., 2015; Huang et al., 2025; Ihle et al., 2025; Sievers et al., 2018).

Given the wide range of pollutants present, advanced analytical techniques are essential for comprehensive assessment of multiple contaminant classes in pond water. Ultra-high performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS/MS) enables sensitive and selective detection of pesticides and mycotoxins at trace levels (Goessens et al., 2022, 2021). UHPLC-Orbitrap high-resolution (HR) MS allows both targeted and untargeted screening of complex mixtures, as demonstrated for antimicrobials in amphibian breeding ponds (Goessens et al., 2020a,b). Inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) and ICP-MS provide precise quantification of metals, while ion chromatography (IC) measures key nutrients (Cl^- , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , PO_4^{3-} , SO_4^{2-}) as indicators of eutrophication and nutrient loading (Bai et al., 2022; Munkhsuld et al., 2024; Tsaturyan et al., 2024). The integration of these platforms enables a thorough characterization of pond chemical composition, facilitating the evaluation of contaminant impacts on pond health and amphibian populations.

This study aimed to quantify environmental contaminants across six chemical classes in breeding ponds in Flanders (Belgium) and to assess how contaminant exposure relates to the status of local common toad populations.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sampling

Twenty breeding ponds in Flanders (Belgium), including 10 ponds with a non-declining (stable or increasing) population size, and 10 ponds with a declining population size, were selected based upon a trend analysis of long-term monitoring data collected by toad patrols during migration (Fig. S1) (Blomme et al., 2026). Pond depths ranged between 0.8 and >1.35 m. Grab water samples were collected at three timepoints: shortly after egg deposition (March 2024), during larval development (May 2024) and at the end of metamorphosis (June 2024). This allowed for temporal analysis, providing insights into how different aquatic life stages of toads were affected by environmental contaminants. Each grab water sample was composed of three subsamples taken at equal distances from one another from the water surface. Following a previously validated approach, two subsamples were collected less than 1 m from the shore, and the third was taken at a distance greater than 1 m (Fig. S2) (Goessens et al., 2022). Pooling these subsamples into a composite

sample increased the likelihood of accurately representing the pond's overall water quality. All pooled samples were filtered on site using a 250 μm mesh sieve (Retsch® sieve, Novolab NV, Belgium, 250 μm , 50 × 200 mm) to remove organic material. Subsequently, the composite sample was divided into separate containers suitable for each analysis. Polypropylene plastic bottles were used for the storage of 0.5 L of water samples for the analysis of metals and nutrients. For the metals analysis, samples were acidified (pH = 2) with HNO_3 upon arrival at the lab to prevent precipitation of metal ions, sorption to the walls of the container and microbial activity which could alter metals content during storage. Furthermore, amber glass bottles were used to collect 0.5 L of water for the analysis of antimicrobial drugs, antiparasitic drugs, mycotoxins and pesticides. Prior to sample collection, each of these bottles were rinsed with 1.0 M ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) to prevent tetracyclines from forming complexes with Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and any remaining metal ions. All samples were kept on ice during transport and subsequently stored at 4 °C up to 4 days before analysis, or at -20 °C for a maximum of one week till analysis.

2.2. Pesticide analysis

A multi-analyte analysis of 87 pesticides, including herbicides, insecticides and fungicides, was performed using SPE and UHPLC-MS/MS, based on an existing method specifically developed and validated for pond water samples, and expanded with 23 pesticides of emerging concern, according to literature (Goessens et al., 2022; Hoendervangers et al., 2025). Accuracy and precision, expressed as coefficient of variation (CV), were reevaluated and found suitable only if between 60 and 120%, and <30%, respectively, according to SANTE guidelines (Table S1). In brief, 0.5 L water samples were filtered using glass microfiber filters (0.45 μm , 90 × 90 mm, Whatman™, UK), followed by a reversed phase (RP) SPE using Sep-Pak®C18 classic cartridges (0.85 mL, 360 mg, Waters, Belgium). Cartridges were washed using 2 mL of methanol and 2 mL of HPLC grade water, after which samples were pumped through the cartridges and eluted using 10 mL of acetonitrile (ACN). The eluate was evaporated under vacuum until dryness using a rotavapor (Büchi Rotavapor R-200, Switzerland) and reconstituted in 2 mL of ACN/water (10/90, v/v). The resulting extract was transferred to a glass vial and stored at -20 °C until analysis using a UHPLC-MS/MS Xevo® TQS system (Waters, USA) with electrospray ionization (ESI). External calibration curves and single standard addition were used for quantification. The limit of detection (LOD) ranged between 0.6 and 1.2 ng/L and the limit of quantification (LOQ) was 8 ng/L.

2.3. Mycotoxins and antiparasitic drug analysis

A validated multi-analyte method using SPE and UHPLC-MS/MS was applied for the targeted analysis of 20 mycotoxins (Goessens et al., 2021) and 15 antiparasitic drugs (Goessens et al., 2020a,b), including 12 coccidiostats and 3 anthelmintics (Table S2). After filtration using a glass microfiber filter (0.45 μm , 90 × 90 mm, Whatman™, UK), 0.5 L of water samples were applied onto an Oasis® HLB SPE cartridge (6 mL, 500 mg, Waters, Belgium) previously conditioned with 6 mL of methanol and 6 mL of Milli-Q water, followed by vacuum-assisted extraction and elution with 5 mL of methanol and 5 mL of methanol acidified with 0.1% formic acid. The combined eluate was vortexed and 200 μL was transferred to a vial containing 50 μL of ultrapure water. The extracts were analysed using an Acquity H-Class UHPLC system connected to a Waters Xevo® TQ-XS MS/MS (Waters, USA), which featured an ESI interface operating in both positive and negative modes. Quantification was performed using matrix-matched calibration curves and suitable internal standards. LODs ranged between 0.04 (enniatin B) and 40 ng/L (levamisole), and LOQs ranged between 1 and 125 ng/L, except for levamisole with an LOQ of 250 ng/L.

2.4. Antimicrobial drug analysis

Using a previously validated method, 52 target antimicrobial drugs belonging to major classes (cephalosporins, diaminopyrimidines, lincosamides, macrolides, nitrofurans, penicillins, phenicols, pleuromutilins, quinolones, sulfonamides and tetracyclines) were analysed using UHPLC-Orbitrap-HRMS (Table S2) (Goessens et al., 2020a,b). The sample preparation consisted of a filtration step using a glass microfiber filter (0.45 µm, 90 × 90 mm, Whatman™, UK) and vacuum-assisted extraction of the 0.5 L sample using an Oasis® HLB SPE cartridge (6 ml, 500 mg, Waters, Belgium), which was previously conditioned with 3 mL of methanol and 7 mL of Milli-Q water. Elution was carried out using 3.5 mL of methanol/ACN/methyl tert-butyl ether (33%, v/v/v) alkalized with 0.1% ammonia 25% solution, followed by 3.5 mL of methanol/ACN/methyl tert-butyl ether (33%, v/v/v) acidified with 0.1% formic acid. The combined eluate was then evaporated to dryness, and the residue was reconstituted in 150 µL of a methanol/ultrapure water solution (2:1, v/v). Analysis was performed using an Ultimate 3000 XRS UHPLC system coupled to a Q-Exact™ HRMS instrument (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), which was operated using heated ESI in positive and negative mode.

Full-scan MS data were acquired to perform additional suspect screening against an in-house database of 265 compounds (Table S3), consisting of pharmaceuticals used in veterinary and/or human medicine, personal care products, additional pesticides not included in the targeted analysis, and substances included in EU Watch List 2025 (European Commission, 2025). Suspect screening was performed using Compound Discoverer 3.3 software (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), within a scan range of 100 to 900 Da and retention time (RT) limits of 0.5 to 10 min. Detected compounds were tentatively identified based on *m/z*-value, accounting for a maximum mass deviation of 3 ppm and minimum signal intensity of 1×10^7 , ensuring only relevant, quantifiable features were considered (Goessens et al., 2025).

In addition, the presence of the ^{13}C isotope and a stable $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$ -ratio were confirmed in order to obtain a tentative identification (level 3) (Schymanski et al., 2014).

2.5. Metal analysis

Eleven elements, including ten metals (Al, Cd, Cr, Cu, Fe, Hg, Mn, Ni, Pb, and Zn) and one metalloid (As), were quantified using ICP-MS (Cd, Cr, Cu, Fe, Hg, Pb and As) and ICP-OES (Al, Fe, Mn, and Zn). For consistency, As is referred to as a “metal” throughout this manuscript, although it is technically a metalloid. Water samples were digested using an *aqua regia* digestion procedure to transform all organically or inorganically bound metals to soluble salts. This procedure enables the quantification of the total recoverable metal concentrations. The method was derived from the Compendium for Water Analysis, provided by the Flemish government for sampling and analysis of metals in water (WAC, 2025), and is compliant with European guidelines (European Commission, 2009). To digest the samples, 6 mL of hydrochloric acid and 2 mL of nitric acid were added to 25.0 mL ± 0.1 mL of each acidified (pH = 2) water sample. Then, samples were slowly heated on a hot plate until the boiling point was reached (103 °C), after which the temperature was maintained for 2 h. Following a cooling period, the digestate was transferred quantitatively to 50 mL falcon tubes and ultrapure Milli-Q water (Merck, Belgium) was added to obtain a total volume of 50 mL. The quality of analysis was assured by including a duplicate of suitable matrix reference material (EnviroMAT-Waste Water Low, SCP Science, France) in each batch of 20 samples. Recovery was calculated by dividing measured concentrations by the theoretical concentration of the matrix reference, resulting in a satisfactory recovery ranging from 82% (Pb) to 113% (Cr). The CV was determined by analysing two random samples in triplicate in each batch. The CV ranged from 2% to 26% in samples analysed using ICP-OES, and between 6% and 29% using ICP-MS. In addition, blank samples were included to check for

potential contamination during the digestion process. To compensate for matrix effects, yttrium was used as internal standard and matrix-matched calibration curves were used for quantification. ICP-OES was executed using an iCAP™ Pro X Duo ICP-OES combined with a CETAC ASX-560 autosampler. LOD values ranged from 1.6 µg/L to 2.8 µg/L, and LOQs ranged from 5.3 µg/L to 9.3 µg/L. Trace metals like Cr, Ni, Cu, As, Cd, Hg and Pb were analysed using the more sensitive iCAP™ MSX single Quadrupole ICP-MS, with LODs ranging from 9.1 to 183.6 ng/L and LOQs from 30.4 to 612.0 ng/L.

2.6. Nutrient analysis

IC was used for the analysis of various nutrients (Cl^- , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , PO_4^{3-} and SO_4^{2-}), following an extra syringe filtration step by means of a Cellulose Acetate Membrane Syringe Filter (25 mm, 0.45 µm, VWR International, USA). The analysis was conducted using a 930 Compact IC Flex and 858 professional sample processor (Metrohm, USA), following the procedure described in the Compendium for Water Analysis (WAC, 2025), which is based on ISO I.O. for S., 2007). LODs ranged from 90 to 200 µg/L.

2.7. Statistical analysis

Prior to statistical analysis, concentrations below the LOQ and LOD were replaced by the respective half values (Johnson, 2018). For each sampling time point, the mean concentration of each detected contaminant was calculated across all ponds to characterize overall concentration levels. Contaminant occurrence was quantified as the percentage of ponds in which each contaminant was detected at that time point. Statistical analyses were conducted in R version 4.4.1. The statistical analysis aimed to investigate whether toad population status could be linked to contaminant concentrations and the number of detected contaminants in water samples of their respective breeding ponds. Since contamination was considered to be a major driver of amphibian population declines, it was expected that higher concentrations or a larger number of contaminants would be present in declining populations. In addition, it was hypothesized that contaminant exposure would differ between stages of toad development (egg, larvae, metamorphosis), and thus concentrations would vary over the sampled timepoints.

2.7.1. Local effects

A heatmap was used to visualize the co-occurrence of multiple contaminants in a single pond and explore relative concentration differences between individual ponds. For each pond, the mean concentration of every contaminant was calculated from the measurements of the three timepoints. Only contaminants that were detected in at least one pond were included in the heatmap. All data were standardized using the z-score to allow for the comparison of contaminants with varying concentration units and scales across different pond locations. The heatmap was created using R package ‘ggplot2’, using the functions ggplot, geom_tile and scale_fill_gradient2 (Wickham, 2016).

2.7.2. Declining versus non-declining populations

As an exploratory analysis to visualize patterns in contaminant composition and to assess whether samples clustered together, a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed. A cut-off was applied to the data by only including contaminants which were detected in at least 10 samples. The mean concentration of each contaminant in each pond was calculated from the concentrations of the three timepoints, and a log transformation was applied to reduce the impact of extreme values. In addition, centring and scaling were applied and the PCA was conducted using the function ‘rda’ in the ‘vegan’ package (Oksanen et al., 2025). The proportion of variance explained by each PC was calculated, as well as the contribution of each contaminant to the PCs. Using a biplot, the PC scores (dots) and the loadings of the variables (vectors) were visualized.

Table 1

Mean concentration (C_{mean} , $\mu\text{g/L}$), standard deviation (SD, $\mu\text{g/L}$) and occurrence (Occ., %) of environmental contaminants in water samples of 20 common toad breeding ponds in Flanders (Belgium), and maximum concentration (C_{max} , $\mu\text{g/L}$) detected across all timepoints.

Metals	March			May			June			C_{max}
	C_{mean}	SD	Occ.	C_{mean}	SD	Occ.	C_{mean}	SD	Occ.	
Al	134.1	161.7	60	371.4	405.8	90	431.1	1307	50	6067
As	2.050	0.860	100	2.550	1.910	100	2.710	1.740	100	10.40
Cd	0.060	0.080	65	0.030	0.040	50	0.050	0.090	55	0.410
Cr	2.150	2.050	90	1.170	3.320	25	2.440	3.750	75	15.05
Cu	2.900	3.810	50	57.80	118.7	55	32.78	113.0	25	520.0
Fe	634.2	484.8	100	844.9	1108	70	1434	1601	95	7382
Mn	270.0	148.6	100	527.9	331.1	100	513.9	406.4	100	1524
Ni	3.000	2.030	100	4.880	10.34	90	2.290	2.160	85	48.25
Pb	2.380	1.950	100	1.350	4.380	30	27.89	114.4	60	526.5
Zn	14.55	10.97	100	14.03	36.80	65	23.08	41.62	95	200.2
Coccidiostats and anthelmintics										
Amprolium	<LOD	-	0	0.0007	0.0001	5	0.0008	0.0006	5	0.0032
Diclazuril	<LOD	-	0	0.0032	0.0050	20	<LOD	-	0	0.0202
Dinitrocarbanilide	0.0078	0.0098	40	0.0068	0.0100	30	0.0012	0.0013	10	0.0268
Lasalocid	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	0.0017	0.0040	5	0.0189
Monensin	<LOD	-	0	0.0023	0.0009	10	<LOD	-	0	0.0050
Antimicrobial drugs										
4-Epichlortetracycline	0.0193	0.0100	25	0.0184	0.0126	10	0.0180	0.0046	30	0.0727
4-Epoxytetracycline	0.0155	0.0020	5	0.0155	0.0022	5	<LOD	-	0	0.0250
Cefoperazone	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	0.0165	0.0036	15	0.0250
Chlortetracycline	0.0223	0.0090	10	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	0.0615
Diketopiperazine	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	0.0155	0.0022	5	0.0250
Doxycycline	0.0617	0.1780	40	0.0194	0.0192	5	0.0160	0.0030	10	0.8366
Nafcillin	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	0.0160	0.0030	10	0.0250
Nalidixic acid	<LOD	-	0	0.0108	0.0033	5	<LOD	-	0	0.0250
Nitrofurantoin	<LOD	-	0	0.0338	0.0547	30	<LOD	-	0	0.2719
Oxytetracycline	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	0.0250
Sulfadiazine	<LOD	-	0	0.0138	0.0065	25	<LOD	-	0	0.0250
Tetracycline	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	0.0160	0.0030	10	0.0250
Trimethoprim	<LOD	-	0	0.0032	0.0050	5	0.0032	0.0050	5	0.0250
Mycotoxins										
α -Zearalanol	<LOD	-	0	0.0012	0.0040	5	<LOD	-	0	0.0186
Aflatoxin B1	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	0.0002	0.0005	5	0.0022
Alternariol monomethyl ether	0.0034	0.0053	10	0.0049	0.0056	25	<LOD	-	0	0.0224
Beauvericin	<LOD	-	10	<LOD	-	0	0.0007	0.0008	25	0.0035
Deepoxy-deoxynivalenol	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	0.0882
Deoxynivalenol	0.0085	0.0130	10	<LOD	-	0	0.0099	0.0088	35	0.0650
Enniatin A	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	0.0101	0.0005	5	0.0125
Enniatin A1	0.0013	0.0011	50	0.0024	0.0017	75	0.0031	0.0021	90	0.0084
Enniatin B	0.0024	0.0020	80	0.0045	0.0031	85	0.0061	0.0035	100	0.0175
Enniatin B1	0.0018	0.0017	65	0.0035	0.0034	75	0.0051	0.0048	95	0.0197
Zearalenone	0.0030	0.0032	10	0.0035	0.0038	15	0.0046	0.0046	25	0.0125
Nutrients										
Cl^-	37266	27728	100	38372	28948	100	38443	25773	100	112872
NO_2^-	110.16	49.288	100	127.86	126.44	100	114.16	66.723	100	679.00
NO_3^-	1624.1	3350.0	100	862.41	1630.7	100	602.34	1067.6	100	13920
PO_4^{3-}	587.29	655.68	100	522.62	600.51	100	782.17	791.67	100	2576.0
SO_4^{2-}	34574	30045	100	32733	32731	100	26829	27343	100	142768
Pesticides										
Amethryn	0.0009	0.0010	10	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	0.0040
Azoxystrobin	0.0111	0.0263	30	0.0021	0.0011	25	0.0022	0.0019	15	0.1140
Benalaxyl	<LOD	-	0	0.0009	0.0010	10	<LOD	-	0	0.0040
Boscalid	0.0074	0.0136	45	0.0024	0.0044	30	<LOD	-	0	0.0533
Carbendazim	<LOD	-	0	0.0033	0.0075	5	0.0025	0.0043	5	0.0359
Chlortoluron	<LOD	-	0	0.0061	0.0198	5	0.0022	0.0028	5	0.0926
Clomazone	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	0.0025	0.0017	55	0.0040
Difenconazole	0.0031	0.0028	40	0.0017	0.0010	15	0.0017	0.0010	15	0.0102
Dimethomorph	0.0011	0.0012	15	0.0009	0.0010	10	<LOD	-	0	0.0040
Diuron	0.0024	0.0005	10	<LOD	-	0	0.0025	0.0014	5	0.0088
Fenoxycarb	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	0.0012	0.0027	5	0.0129
Imazalil	0.0063	0.0214	5	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	0.0996
Imidacloprid	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	0.0022	0.0004	5	0.0040
Metamitron	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	0.0008	0.0007	5	0.0040
Methomyl	0.0072	0.0243	5	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	0.1130
Penconazole	0.0008	0.0007	5	<LOD	-	0	0.0009	0.0010	10	0.0040
Piperonylbutoxide	0.0011	0.0012	15	0.0011	0.0012	15	0.0024	0.0039	25	0.0162
Propiconazole	0.0018	0.0018	40	0.0010	0.0013	15	0.0021	0.0042	25	0.0195
Prosulfocarb	0.0253	0.0156	100	0.0066	0.0042	75	0.0127	0.0095	90	0.0640
Pyrimethanil	0.0025	0.0030	35	0.0019	0.0023	20	0.0014	0.0011	15	0.0142
Spinosad A	0.0057	0.0105	5	<LOD	-	0	<LOD	-	0	0.0513
Tebuconazole	0.0053	0.0085	35	0.0030	0.0023	50	0.0040	0.0080	40	0.0385
Tebufozide	0.0008	0.0007	5	0.0008	0.0007	5	0.0008	0.0007	5	0.0040

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Metals	March			May			June			
	C _{mean}	SD	Occ.	C _{mean}	SD	Occ.	C _{mean}	SD	Occ.	C _{max}
Terbuthylazine	0.0079	0.0202	5	0.0033	0.0002	5	0.0033	0.0002	5	0.0960
Thiodicarb	0.0012	0.0006	5	0.0030	0.0026	45	<LOD	-	0	0.0102

Note: <LOD = below limit of detection; - = not calculated, as the compound was not detected in any of samples at this timepoint.

To investigate whether population status could be linked to contamination of the breeding ponds, contaminant concentrations in ponds with declining and non-declining populations were compared. Few studies have examined the relative importance of individual contaminants within environmentally relevant mixtures with respect to their effects on amphibians. As a result, no specific compounds could be prioritized, and we chose to investigate all contaminants for which at least 10 detectable measurements were available. To maintain consistency and minimize the need for extensive multiple-testing corrections, a limma (linear models for microarray data) analysis was applied to all contaminant groups, rather than using separate univariate analyses. This method has been previously employed in LC-MS metabolomics and environmental exposure studies (Black et al., 2025; Smith et al., 2019; Yu et al., 2021). Limma fits linear models to each contaminant while employing an empirical Bayes approach to shrink individual compound variances - particularly those estimated from small sample sizes - toward a common value derived from all contaminants. This “borrowing of information” increases statistical power relative to standard pairwise comparisons (Ritchie et al., 2015). For repeated-measures data, the ‘dream’ (differential expression for repeated measures) Bioconductor package was used (Hoffman and Roussos, 2021). The chosen model formula included population status as a fixed effect and pond location as a random effect to account for repeated measures. P-values were adjusted for multiple testing using the Benjamini-Hochberg correction, with values < 0.05 considered statistically significant.

2.7.3. Temporal trends

In addition to pond-to-pond differences, contaminant concentrations were expected to vary across toad developmental stages within ponds. To assess this, pairwise comparisons of log-transformed contaminant concentrations were performed for all compounds detected in at least 10 samples. The non-parametric paired Wilcoxon test was used to compare the three sampling time points (March, May, and June 2024). Benjamini-Hochberg correction was again applied to account for multiple testing, and p-values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Table 2

Overview of 15 compounds tentatively identified by the suspect screening of water samples of 20 common toad breeding ponds in Flanders (Belgium). Identification was based on exact mass (mass deviation < 3 ppm), presence of the ¹³C isotope and stable ¹³C/¹²C-ratio. The occurrence of each contaminant in the 60 water samples, collected from 20 ponds at 3 timepoints, is presented as the percentage (Occ., %) of samples containing the tentatively identified compound. The accurate mass (*m/z*, Da), ionization mode and retention time (RT, min) are presented for each compound.

Type of contaminant	Tentatively identified compound	Occ.	<i>m/z</i> (Da)	Ionization mode	RT (min)
Herbicides	Ethofumesate	5	285.08048	[M-H] ⁻¹	6.54
Insect repellents	DEET	2	192.13824	[M+H] ⁺¹	6.36
	Icaridin	12	230.17500	[M+H] ⁺¹	7.81
Pharmaceuticals	Atenolol	2	267.17002	[M+H] ⁺¹	3.07
	Bisoprolol	3	326.23234	[M+H] ⁺¹	6.53
	Cortisone	3	361.20081	[M+H] ⁺¹	9.02
	Diazepam	2	283.06501	[M-H] ⁻¹	6.17
	Ibuprofen	5	207.13777	[M+H] ⁺¹	7.23
	Norethindrone	5	299.20038	[M+H] ⁺¹	9.26
	Simvastatin	2	419.27860	[M+H] ⁺¹	9.11
	Sulfamethoxy-pyridazine	3	281.07002	[M+H] ⁺¹	3.07
	Toraseamide	2	347.11844	[M-H] ⁻¹	5.81
	Valsartan	5	436.23377	[M+H] ⁺¹	8.09
Personal care products	Ethylhexyl methoxycinnamate	7	291.19525	[M+H] ⁺¹	8.09
	Butylparaben	3	193.08699	[M-H] ⁻¹	6.85

3. Results & discussion

3.1. Multi-compound analysis exposes widespread environmental contamination

3.1.1. Targeted analysis

An overview of the detected contaminants and their concentrations is presented in Table 1.

A total of 25 pesticides were detected, most of which occurred sporadically. Overall occurrence was calculated as the percentage of ponds in which a contaminant was detected at least once during the entire sampling period. Based on this metric, prosulfocarb (100%), clomazone (55%) tebuconazole (50%), and boscalid (45%) were the most frequently detected per sampling point. The highest concentrations were measured for azoxystrobin (113.9 ng/L), methomyl (113.0 ng/L), imazalil (99.6 ng/L), terbuthylazine (96.0 ng/L), and chlortoluron (92.6 ng/L). Thus, peak levels of azoxystrobin and methomyl exceeded the Belgian drinking water threshold of 100 ng/L (Vlarem II, 1995), although no limits exist for ponds. These concentration ranges are consistent with recent assessments of European surface waters, where individual pesticides rarely exceed 100 ng/L (Casado et al., 2019; Navarro et al., 2024). Comparable mixture complexity has been reported, although most studies focus on rivers rather than lentic habitats (Conseil et al., 2024; Goessens et al., 2022; Slaby et al., 2023). The dominant compounds also largely matched results from other European countries, including terbuthylazine, prosulfocarb, tebuconazole, and chlortoluron (Casado et al., 2019; Conseil et al., 2024; Guibal et al., 2017). However, azoxystrobin, imazalil and methomyl occurred at relatively high levels in our study only, which is likely due to regional differences in agricultural use.

Among mycotoxins, 11 compounds were detected. Enniatin B (ENNB), enniatin B1 (ENNB1) and enniatin A1 (ENNA1) were present in all ponds, while deoxynivalenol (DON) and deepoxy-deoxynivalenol (DOM-1) reached the highest concentrations (65.0 and 88.2 ng/L, respectively). These findings align with previous reports from Flemish ponds (Goessens et al., 2022) and levels found in European rivers (Bucheli et al., 2008; Kolpin et al., 2014).

Likewise, five antiparasitic drugs were detected, with dinirocarbanilide being both most frequent (40%) and highest in concentration (26.8 ng/L), comparable to the dominant antiparasitic compounds reported by Goessens et al. (2022).

Thirteen antimicrobial drugs were detected, with doxycycline (40%) and 4-epichlortetracycline (30%) being most abundant, reaching 836.6 ng/L and 72.7 ng/L, respectively. These findings mirror patterns seen in Belgium and France, where tetracyclines are commonly recorded and likely originate from veterinary use and manure leaching (Bouissou-Schurtz et al., 2014; Goessens et al., 2022).

Ten metals were detected, with all ponds containing Al, As, Cr, Fe, Mn, Ni, Pb and Zn during at least one of the sampling timepoints, and detection frequencies ranging between 100 and 25%. The highest total recoverable metal concentrations were recorded for Fe (7382.1 µg/L), Mn (1524.0 µg/L) and Al (6066.6 µg/L), and notable peaks occurred for Cu (520.0 µg/L) and Pb (526.5 µg/L). Average concentrations of Cr, Ni, Cu, As, Pb and Zn exceeded Flemish annual limits in multiple ponds (Vlarem II, 1995) (Table S4). While most metals occurred within ranges typical for European surface waters (Eklöf et al., 2024), Fe, Cu and Mn were present at elevated levels relative to reported continental averages. Nutrient concentrations (Cl^- , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , PO_4^{3-} and SO_4^{2-}) generally fell within permitted limits based on national and EU guidelines (European Parliament, 2008, 2000; Vlarem II, 1995), with total nitrogen <2 mg/L and phosphorus <0.1 mg/L.

Overall, the mixture complexity and concentration ranges observed in these Flemish ponds are consistent with broader European patterns, where no clear regional contamination trends exist and small water bodies typically harbour diverse multi-class contaminant mixtures (Casado et al., 2019; Schreiner et al., 2016).

From an ecotoxicological perspective, the detected concentrations of pesticides, antiparasitic drugs, mycotoxins, antimicrobials and most metals (As, Cd, Cr, Mn, Ni) fall within ranges previously reported to pose little risk to aquatic organisms, including amphibians and invertebrates (Goessens et al., 2022), and remain well below harmful levels documented for several amphibian species such as *Boana faber*, *Rhinella arenarum*, *Xenopus laevis*, *Pelophylax nigromaculatus* and *Bufo gargarizans*, as well as aquatic invertebrates including *Daphnia magna*, *Ceriodaphnia silvestrii* and *Danio rerio* (Acquaroni et al., 2024; Castelhana Gebara et al., 2021; Felice et al., 2025; Huang et al., 2020, 2025; Ihle et al., 2025; Wang et al., 2017; Warsneski et al., 2024). However, some metals (Fe, Cu, Al, Pb and Zn) reached mean or peak concentrations exceeding those shown experimentally to impair development, induce malformations or cause mortality in certain amphibian taxa (Castelhana Gebara et al., 2021; Sievers et al., 2018; Veronez et al., 2016), although sensitivity varies widely between species, populations and developmental stages (Adams et al., 2021a; Kerby et al., 2010). This variability makes direct toxicological inference uncertain. Moreover, the bioavailable fraction of metals is likely substantially lower than the total concentrations measured, as only a portion of metals in water occur in dissolved or otherwise biologically available forms. The concentrations reported here were obtained using an *aqua regia* digestion prior to ICP-MS and ICP-OES analysis, which is a standard procedure for water quality assessment and enables comparison with general surface water quality guidelines. However, this approach quantifies total recoverable metal concentrations and therefore likely overestimates the actual exposure experienced by aquatic organisms in the ponds (Merrington et al., 2016). In addition, contaminant levels represent only a temporal snapshot, whereas metal concentrations in European surface waters are

Fig. 1. Heatmap of centred and scaled contaminant concentrations in water samples of 20 common toad breeding ponds in Flanders (Belgium), divided into 10 ponds with declining and 10 ponds with non-declining populations. The scoring corresponding colour gradient reflects the value's distance from the mean in units of standard deviation. Red coloured tiles (score >0) indicate a concentration which is higher than the variable's mean, white tiles show a score = 0, while blue tiles (score <0) show values below the mean. Only contaminants that were detected in at least one pond are included in the heatmap. 4-EOTC = 4-epioxytetracycline, 4-ECTC = 4-epichlortetracycline, DON = deoxynivalenol, DOM-1 = deepoxy-deoxynivalenol, AFB1 = aflatoxin B1, ENNA1 = enniatin A1, ENNB = enniatin B, ENNA = enniatin A, ENNB1 = enniatin B1, BEA = beauvericin, a-ZAL = α -zearalanol, ZEN = zearalenone, AME = alternariol monomethyl ether. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. Map of all sampled pond locations, visualized with a color scale indicating the total number of pesticides, antimicrobial drugs, coccidiostats, anthelmintic drugs and mycotoxins detected at that location during the sampling period (March-June 2024). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. Principal component analysis (PCA) of mean contaminant concentrations in 20 common toad breeding ponds in Flanders (Belgium) (a), and additional PCA following the removal of a population showing extreme values (b). PC1 and PC2 capture 31% of the total variation in the data. The dots represent the principal component scores of the ponds, with colours indicating the population status. The vectors represent the different contaminant concentrations. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

known to fluctuate strongly due to changes in deposition, pH and organic carbon content (Eklöf et al., 2024). Nutrient concentrations remained within regulatory limits (Vlarem II, 1995), though maximum nitrite and nitrate levels surpassed thresholds reported to affect development or species interactions in some amphibians (Griffis-Kyle, 2005; Smith et al., 2005). However, these concentrations remained below toxicity levels reported for the common toad (Dimitrova and Lukanov, 2024; Macías et al., 2007; Ortiz et al., 2004), suggesting species-specific tolerance. Taken together, while most contaminant levels are unlikely to cause acute toxic effects, exceedances of experimental toxicity thresholds for some metals and nutrients highlight the need for caution, long-term monitoring and bioavailability-focused assessment before

ruling out potential ecological impacts.

3.1.2. Suspect screening

In addition to the contaminants detected through targeted analyses, 15 additional compounds were tentatively identified via suspect screening. Following the approach of Schymanski et al. (2014), these compounds were assigned a level 3 “probable structure,” as candidates were tentatively identified based on their exact mass (deviation <3 ppm), the presence of the ^{13}C isotope, and a stable $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$ ratio. The suspects included one herbicide (ethofumesate); two insect repellents (DEET and icaridin); 10 pharmaceuticals for human and/or veterinary use, including atenolol, bisoprolol, cortisone, diazepam, ibuprofen,

Table 3

Pairwise comparison of contaminant concentrations between months in water samples of 20 common toad breeding ponds in Flanders (Belgium). Significant differences with adjusted p-value <0.05 are indicated with (*).

Metals	March - May	May - June	March - June
Al	0.0036 (*)	0.0200 (*)	0.7764
Cu	0.0370 (*)	0.1860	0.4500
Fe	0.7230	0.1240	0.0090 (*)
Mn	0.0140 (*)	0.3800	0.0390 (*)
Pb	0.0055 (*)	0.0668	0.3225
Zn	0.0750	0.0360 (*)	0.9260
Pesticides			
Boscalid	0.0430 (*)	0.0390 (*)	0.0240 (*)
Prosulfocarb	0.0003(*)	0.0069 (*)	0.0027(*)
Thiodicarb	0.0160 (*)	1.0000	0.0160 (*)
Mycotoxins			
Enniatin A1	0.0234 (*)	0.1531	0.0098 (*)
Enniatin B	0.0126 (*)	0.0149 (*)	0.0013 (*)
Enniatin B1	0.0325 (*)	0.0593	0.0093 (*)
Nutrients			
NO ₃ ⁻	0.1130	0.0180 (*)	0.0200 (*)
SO ₄ ²⁻	0.0270 (*)	0.0550	0.0270 (*)

norethindrone, simvastatin, sulfamethoxypyridazine, torasemide and valsartan; and two chemicals found in personal care products: ethylhexyl methoxycinnamate and butylparaben (Table 2). The suspect screening data were excluded from the statistical analysis because fewer than 10 detections per compound were obtained. Although suspect identities could, in principle, be confirmed by comparing retention times with purchased reference standards (level 1 confirmation), this was beyond the scope of the present study, as it would not have contributed to the statistical testing of our hypotheses. Instead, the suspect screening serves as an exploratory analysis to identify compounds of interest which could be the focus of future targeted analyses.

Several reasons likely explain why only a limited number of household contaminants and human pharmaceuticals were detected. First, the extraction protocol used for the suspect screening was optimized and validated for antimicrobial drugs, and may not effectively recover other compound classes. Second, many of these substances typically occur at very low concentrations, and poor recovery could have hindered their detection using the current method. Third, both spatial heterogeneity within ponds and temporal variability in pollution loads may not have been fully captured by the selected sampling locations and timing.

3.2. Local effects

Fig. 1 presents a heatmap summarizing the concentrations of all detected contaminants in each pond. No clear pattern was observed to confirm our hypothesis that specific contaminants occurred more frequently or at higher concentrations in ponds with declining populations compared to those with non-declining populations. This indicates that ponds with declining and non-declining populations do not have distinct contamination profiles, and that there is substantial variation in contamination levels within both groups. All ponds contained multiple contaminants at low concentrations, with substantial variation in both the types and numbers of compounds per pond. The number of detected compounds showed little geographic variation, suggesting that co-occurrence of multiple contaminants was widespread across all ponds (Fig. 2). Notably, a total of 19 different compounds - including 14 pesticides, 1 pharmaceutical, and 4 mycotoxins - was detected in a single pond with a declining population (location 'M'; Fig. 2). Although individual pesticide concentrations remained in the low ng/L range in this pond, their combined average concentrations reached 205 ng/L, exceeding the Belgian drinking water quality guideline of 100 ng/L (Vlarem II, 1995). In comparison, other ponds, including location 'W' (declining population) and 'C' (non-declining population), had maximum total pesticide concentrations of 73 ng/L and 74 ng/L respectively.

3.3. Linking contaminant concentrations to population decline

Using PCA, patterns in contaminant composition were visualized to explore potential clustering of ponds (Fig. 3). However, the resulting estimates did not capture a substantial portion of the total variation in the data. The first and second principal components together explained only 31% of the total variation, and no clear separation was observed between ponds with declining and non-declining populations (Fig. 3a). After removing pond M, which showed extreme values even after log transformation, similar patterns were obtained (Fig. 3b). This lack of clustering indicates that contaminant profiles vary widely between ponds, and there is no clear separation between ponds with declining and non-declining populations, based on their contaminant profiles. In agreement with these results, the limma analysis revealed no significant differences in the concentrations or the number of detected contaminants between the two pond groups (adjusted p-values >0.05). Importantly, the absence of statistically significant differences indicates that no difference in contamination levels was detected in this study and within the limits of current dataset, but it does not exclude the possibility that contaminants contribute to population declines through subtle, cumulative, or unmeasured mechanisms. The ability to detect differences in contaminant exposure between groups is influenced by sample size, within-group variability, and effect magnitude. While the present study was not specifically designed to maximize statistical power for all detected compounds, the use of the limma framework incorporates empirical Bayes variance shrinkage, which improves sensitivity and stability of differential analyses in studies with moderate sample sizes and high dimensional data. Nevertheless, statistical power is likely reduced for compounds exhibiting high temporal or spatial variability or low overall concentrations. Accordingly, results should be interpreted with caution, and the study is therefore best suited to detect moderate to large differences in exposure between groups rather than subtle effects.

These findings indicate that the measured contaminants in surface waters of breeding ponds do not show an obvious association with common toad population decline. Results therefore align with previous studies that also found no clear link between amphibian population trends and contaminant loads in aquatic environments. For example, Davidson et al. (2012) reported that contaminant concentrations in *Rana cascadae* tadpoles were not significantly different between stable versus declining populations. It is important to note, however, that both our analysis and similar studies focus on the effects of individual substances, while all ponds contained complex mixtures of contaminants. Due to this limitation, mixture effects may have been overlooked, leading to a possible underestimation of the total toxicity of detected mixtures. The potential ecotoxicological impacts of environmentally realistic mixtures remain difficult to assess, given the vast number of possible combinations and limited toxicity data for most individual compounds (Godoy et al., 2014; Kidd et al., 2024). Toxicity data is lacking for the common toad specifically and toxicity assessments generally focus on only one of the stages of the complex amphibian development. Unique mixtures were detected in each pond and toxicity data was lacking for many of the mixture constituents, hindering estimation of the overall mixture toxicity based on data of individual chemicals. Furthermore, estimation of the ecotoxicological impact of mixtures is complicated further due to potential interactions between contaminants, which can cause the toxicity of the mixture to be greater (synergy) or less than expected (antagonism) using a response or concentration addition model (Heys et al., 2016). Due to these issues, there is a growing use of integrated chemical and effect-based monitoring, in which the effects of detected contaminant mixtures are directly assessed in an exposure study. For example, Peluso et al. (2023) introduced an alternative approach combining chemical water analysis with experimental exposure of an amphibian species (*Rana arenarum*) to pond water, providing a more realistic assessment of mixture toxicity. Such approaches could improve future evaluations of mixture-related risks in amphibians. Alternatively,

Fig. 4. Boxplots showing the decrease in concentrations of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} in water samples over time in 20 common toad breeding ponds in Flanders (Belgium). Samples were taken at three timepoints representing different stages of toad development, indicated on the plots as timepoint 1 (March), 2 (May) and 3 (June). Significantly different concentrations are indicated by (*), while non-significant differences are indicated by 'ns'.

more advanced statistical approaches may be used in future studies to relate high-dimensional exposure mixtures to demographic metrics, such as population status (Zhu et al., 2024).

In addition, this work focused only on selected classes of environmental contaminants, while others such as PAHs, PCBs, PFAS, microplastics, personal care products, and pharmaceuticals were either not targeted or only tentatively identified in suspect screening. Moreover, contaminant levels likely vary spatially and temporally, and single-location sampling may not fully capture this variability. In addition, there is a mismatch in the biological and temporal scales of our short-term water quality assessment and the long-term population trends, which we aim to link in this study. Due to this mismatch, direct causal inference is limited.

Because this study did not provide strong evidence supporting environmental contamination as the main driver of population decline, other potential causes deserve consideration. Climate-driven changes in food availability, infectious diseases, and habitat fragmentation may play an important role (Beebee, 2013; Hamer et al., 2021). Notably, amphibian decline is widely recognized as multifactorial, and additive or synergistic effects of stressors are often overlooked (Blaustein et al.,

2011; Campbell Grant et al., 2020; Ford et al., 2020). For instance, contaminant exposure combined with pathogens, elevated temperature, predator cues, or salinity can substantially increase harmful effects (Hallman and Brooks, 2016; Kerby et al., 2009; Mandrillon et al., 2006; Pochini and Hoverman, 2017; Quiroga et al., 2024; Relyea, 2003; Rohr et al., 2008; Wood and Welch, 2015).

Finally, it is possible that common toad population decline is not driven by mortality or sublethal effects experienced during larval stage, but rather by contaminant exposure during the post-metamorphic terrestrial life stage. Adult toads are expected to be exposed to environmental contaminants during migration towards their breeding pond, as well as during foraging in summer months (Berger et al., 2012; Churko et al., 2024; Lenhardt et al., 2015). Although the larval stage is generally expected to be the most sensitive life stage, and thus most affected by contaminant exposure, the expected demographic population-level impact of increased mortality during the larval stage in toads is relatively low (Willson et al., 2012). On the other hand, adult survival and clutch size are expected to have more important demographic population-level consequences than larval survival (Willson et al., 2012). Therefore, contaminant exposure could also be assessed in

Fig. 5. Boxplots showing the increase in concentrations of mycotoxins enniatin A1 (ENNA1), enniatin B (ENNB) and enniatin B1 (ENNB1) in water samples over time, in 20 common toad breeding ponds in Flanders (Belgium). Samples were taken at three timepoints representing different stages of toad development, indicated on the plots as timepoint 1 (March), 2 (May) and 3 (June). Significantly different concentrations are indicated by (*), while non-significant differences are indicated by 'ns'.

adult toads to improve our understanding of the impact of environmental contaminants on populations of common toads throughout their life cycle (Nolan et al., 2023).

3.4. Temporal trends

Significant temporal trends were observed for several contaminants, including metals, pesticides, nutrients, and mycotoxins (Table 3), indicating that aquatic exposure varies across different stages of toad development. Peaks in pesticide and metal concentrations were irregular and compound-specific. In March, some ponds exhibited spikes in pesticides such as boscalid and prosulfocarb. May samples showed slightly elevated metal concentrations (Al, Cu, Fe, Mn, Zn) along with a boscalid concentration peak, while June samples revealed further spikes in metals (Al, Fe, Pb, Zn) and prosulfocarb. These fluctuations reflect localized spikes rather than consistent trends across all sampling sites. In contrast, two nutrients (NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-}) and three mycotoxins (ENNA1, ENNB, ENNB1) showed consistent temporal patterns. Concentrations of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} decreased significantly over the sampling period (Fig. 4), while other nutrients remained stable. The most prevalent enniatins (ENNA1, ENNB, ENNB1) steadily increased in concentration over time (Fig. 5). Concentrations of pharmaceuticals remained stable at all sampling points ($p > 0.05$).

Significant changes in pesticide and metal concentrations between March, May, and June likely reflect external influences such as agricultural activity and hydrological conditions. Peaks in pesticide occurrence may be linked to crop management practices (Ulrich et al., 2018), while sudden increases in metals can result from heavy rainfall events that enhance run-off from surrounding land (Chaumet et al., 2022). Besides run-off, other environmental processes - including photodegradation (Drouin et al., 2021), biodegradation (Gruchlik et al., 2018), and sorption or desorption from sediments (Chaumet et al., 2021) - can further influence variability in contaminant concentrations.

In contrast to the fluctuating patterns of metals and pesticides, the observed steady increase in ENNA1, ENNB, and ENNB1 aligns with previously reported seasonal trends in surface waters (Ribeiro et al.,

2015; Schenzel et al., 2012). This suggests increased fungal production of mycotoxins throughout the crop growing season, combined with transport into ponds via precipitation or snowmelt (Kolpin et al., 2014). Supporting this interpretation, recent analyses of wheat in Belgium reported an increase in DON, zearalenone, ENNB, ENNB1, and ENNA1 in 2024, likely driven by an unusually wet spring that promoted fungal growth (Jonard et al., 2025). Additionally, the consistent decline of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} concentrations over the sampling period may be related to elevated early-spring run-off of manure and sediment into ponds, followed by gradual dilution or sedimentation as rainfall decreased.

Overall, these observations indicate that common toad larvae are exposed to a dynamic mixture of contaminants that varies throughout development. Although sampling dates were not selected to capture expected contamination peaks, they provide realistic insight into actual larval exposure during residence in breeding ponds. Given that each measurement represents only a snapshot in time, peaks likely occurred between sampling events and remained undetected. Thus, the three chosen sampling moments may have missed short-term peak exposures, especially for contaminants showing short episodic peaks, such as pesticides and metals. Future studies aiming to characterize temporal dynamics more comprehensively should employ more frequent sampling or passive samplers (Mathon et al., 2022).

4. Conclusion

This study examines the occurrence and prevalence of a wide range of environmental contaminants, including pesticides, mycotoxins, antimicrobial drugs, coccidiostats, anthelmintic drugs, metals and nutrients, in breeding ponds of the European common toad, a widespread species facing consistent population decline in Flanders, Belgium. Complex contaminant mixtures were identified in all ponds at concentrations generally consistent with those reported across Europe. Although the majority of detected compounds were present at levels below established ecotoxicological thresholds for single compounds in amphibians and aquatic invertebrates, episodic peaks in total recoverable metal and nutrient concentrations occasionally exceeded values potentially

associated with adverse biological effects. It is important to note that the detected metal concentrations represent the total recoverable concentration rather than the bio-available fraction, and therefore likely overestimates the actual exposure of aquatic organisms. None of the detected contaminants could be linked directly to toad population status, suggesting that environmental contamination alone is unlikely to explain observed declines. Instead, population decline is likely driven by multiple interacting stressors, including habitat fragmentation, climate change, availability of nutritional resources and disease. The considerable temporal variability in contaminant concentrations further highlights the need for more frequent sampling to capture exposure dynamics more accurately. Future ecotoxicological studies should evaluate the effects of complex contaminant mixtures and additional contaminant classes which could potentially enter the aquatic ecosystem through industrial processes or household use. In addition, contaminant exposure could also be assessed during the terrestrial stage of adult toads to improve our understanding of the true impact of environmental contaminants on populations of common toads throughout their life cycle.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

S. Devliegere: Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **T. Goessens:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **S. De Baere:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology. **E. Blomme:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **A. Barbi:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **E. Meers:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **L. Vanhaecke:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **P. Spanoghe:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **A. Martel:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Conceptualization. **F. Batsleer:** Writing – review & editing. **D. Bonte:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Conceptualization. **F. Pasmans:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **S. Croubels:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This project is supported by the Special Research Fund of Ghent University grant number BOF23/GOA/008 and the Research Foundation – Flanders (FWO, grant number 1204324N and FWO. HMZ.2022.0008.01).

This research has benefitted from a statistical consult with Ghent University FIRE (Fostering Innovative Research based on Evidence).

The authors wish to thank Jelle Lambrecht, Joachim Neri, Liliane Goeteyn, Beata Pomian and Pieter Vantiegheem for their technical contribution to the manuscript.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2026.127785>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Acquaroni, M., Cresto, F.N., Coll, C.P., Svartz, G., 2024. Toxicity assessment of a tebuconazole-based fungicide on the embryo-larval development of the common south American toad *Rhinella arenarum*. *Environ. Toxicol.* 39. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tox.24081>.
- Adams, E., Leeb, C., Brühl, C.A., Adams, E., Leeb, C., Brühl, C.A., 2021a. Pesticide exposure affects reproductive capacity of common toads (*Bufo bufo*) in a viticultural landscape. *Ecotoxicology* 30. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10646-020-02335-9>, 2021 302.
- Adams, E., Leeb, C., Roodt, A.P., Brühl, C.A., Adams, E., Leeb, C., Roodt, A.P., Brühl, C.A., 2021b. Interspecific sensitivity of European amphibians towards two pesticides and comparison to standard test species. *Environ. Sci. Eur.* 33. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-021-00491-1>, 2021 331.
- Albuquerque, V.J. de, Folador, A., Müller, C., Pompermaier, A., Hartmann, M., Hartmann, P.A., 2024. How do different concentrations of aluminum and zinc affect the survival, body size, morphology and immune system of *Physalaemus cuvieri* (Fitzinger, 1826) tadpole? *J. Toxicol. Environ. Health, Part A* 87. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15287394.2024.2311828>.
- Bai, M., Zhang, C., Bai, Y., Wang, T., Qu, S., Qi, H., Zhang, M., Tan, C., Zhang, C., 2022. Occurrence and health risks of heavy metals in drinking water of self-supplied wells in northern China. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19 (19), 12517. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph191912517>.
- Beebee, T.J.C., 2013. Effects of road mortality and mitigation measures on amphibian populations. *Conserv. Biol.* 27. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12063>.
- Berger, G., Graef, F., Pfeffer, H., 2012. Temporal coincidence of migrating amphibians with mineral fertiliser applications on arable fields. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2012.04.006>.
- Berger, G., Graef, F., Pfeffer, H., Berger, G., Graef, F., Pfeffer, H., 2013. Glyphosate applications on arable fields considerably coincide with migrating amphibians. *Sci. Rep.* 3. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep02622>, 2013 31.
- Black, G.P., Anderson, B.N., Wong, L., Alaimo, C.P., He, G., Denison, M.S., Bennett, D.H., Tancredi, D., Durbin-Johnson, B., Hammock, B.D., Chowdhary, P., Rubin, R., Young, T.M., 2025. Comprehensive nontargeted analysis of drinking water supplies to identify chemicals associated with estrogen receptor agonism or present in regions of elevated breast cancer occurrence. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 59. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.4c12204>.
- Blaustein, A.R., Han, B.A., Relyea, R.A., Johnson, P.T.J., Buck, J.C., Gervasi, S.S., Kats, L.B., 2011. The complexity of amphibian population declines: understanding the role of cofactors in driving amphibian losses. *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.* 1223, 108–119. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-6632.2010.05909.x>.
- Blomme, E., Batsleer, F., Matheve, H., Verbelen, D., Martel, A., Croubels, S., Pasmans, F., Bonte, D., 2025. Consistent phenological advancement of common toad migration in response to climate change in Flanders, Belgium. *Amphibia-Reptilia* 46. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15685381-bja10207>.
- Blomme, E., Rommel, H., Batsleer, F., Clement, L., Verbelen, D., Martel, A., et al., 2026. Decline of common toad populations in flanders is not linked to surrounding landscape. *bioRxiv*, 2026-01.
- Bouissou-Schurtz, C., Houeto, P., Guerbet, M., Bachelot, M., Casellas, C., Mauclair, A.-C., Panetier, P., Delval, C., Masset, D., 2014. Ecological risk assessment of the presence of pharmaceutical residues in a French national water survey. *Regul. Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yrtph.2014.04.006>.
- Bucheli, T.D., Wettstein, F.E., Hartmann, N., Erbs, M., Vogelgsang, S., Forrer, H.-R., Schwarzenbach, R.P., 2008. Fusarium mycotoxins: overlooked aquatic micropollutants? *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 56, 1029–1034. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf073082k>.
- Campbell Grant, E.H., Miller, D.A.W., Muths, E., 2020. A synthesis of evidence of drivers of amphibian declines. *Herpetologica* 76. <https://doi.org/10.1655/0018-0831-76.2.101>.
- Casado, J., Brigden, K., Santillo, D., Johnston, P., 2019. Screening of pesticides and veterinary drugs in small streams in the European Union by liquid chromatography high resolution mass spectrometry. *Sci. Total Environ.* 670. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.03.207>.
- Castelhana Gebara, R., de Oliveira Gonçalves Alho, L., Bruno de Abreu, C., da Silva Mansano, A., Moreira, R.A., Swerts Rocha, G., Gama Melão, M. da G., 2021. Toxicity and risk assessment of zinc and aluminum mixtures to *Ceriodaphnia silvestrii* (Crustacea: Cladocera). *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 40. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.5162>.
- Chaumet, B., Probst, J.-L., Eon, P., Camboulive, T., Riboul, D., Payré-Suc, V., Granouillac, F., Probst, A., Chaumet, B., Probst, J.-L., Eon, P., Camboulive, T., Riboul, D., Payré-Suc, V., Granouillac, F., Probst, A., 2021. Role of pond sediments for trapping pesticides in an agricultural catchment (Auradé, SW France): distribution and controlling factors. *Water* 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13131734>, 2021, Page 1734 13.
- Chaumet, B., Probst, J.-L., Payré-Suc, V., Granouillac, F., Riboul, D., Probst, A., 2022. Pond mitigation in dissolved and particulate pesticide transfers: influence of storm events and seasonality (Auradé agricultural catchment, SW-France). *J. Environ. Manag.* 320. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115911>.
- Churko, G., Szerencsits, E., Aldrich, A., Schmidt, B.R., 2024. Spatial analysis of the potential exposure of amphibians to plant protection products at the landscape scale. *Basic Appl. Ecol.* 76, 14–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.baee.2024.02.004>.
- Conseil, G., Milla, S., Cardoso, O., Pasquini, L., Rosin, C., Banas, D., Conseil, G., Milla, S., Cardoso, O., Pasquini, L., Rosin, C., Banas, D., 2024. Occurrence, dispersal, and associated environmental risk assessment of pesticides and their transformation products in small water bodies of Northeastern France. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 31. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-024-35573-z>, 2024 3159.

- Davidson, C., Stanley, K., Simonich, S.M., 2012. Contaminant residues and declines of the Cascades frog (*Rana cascadae*) in the California Cascades, USA. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 31. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.1902>.
- Dimitrova, B., Lukanov, S., 2024. Contrasting effects of ammonium nitrate on tadpole survival, growth and behavior in two common anuran species. *Ecol. Front.* 44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecofro.2024.01.004>.
- Drouin, G., Droz, B., Leresche, F., Payraudeau, S., Masbou, J., Imfeld, G., 2021. Direct and indirect photodegradation of atrazine and S-metolachlor in agriculturally impacted surface water and associated C and N isotope fractionation. *Environ. Sci. Process. Impacts* 23. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1EM00246E>.
- Eklóf, K., Brömssen, C. von, Huser, B., Åkerblom, S., Augustaitis, A., Braaten, H.F.V., Wit, H.A. de, Dirnböck, T., Elustondo, D., Grandin, U., Holubová, A., Kleemola, S., Krám, P., Lundin, L., Löfgren, S., Markensten, H., Moldan, F., Karlsson, G.P., Rönnback, P., et al., 2024. Trends in mercury, lead and cadmium concentrations in 27 European streams and rivers: 2000–2020. *Environ. Pollut.* 360. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2024.124761>.
- European Commission, 2009. Commission directive 2009/90/EC laying down, pursuant to directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, technical specifications for chemical analysis and monitoring of water status (text with EEA relevance). *Off. J. Eur. Union* L201, 36–38.
- European Commission, 2025. Commission implementing decision (EU) 2025/439 of 28 February 2025 establishing a watch list of substances for union-wide monitoring in the field of water policy pursuant to directive 2008/105/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council. *Off. J.*
- European Parliament, 2000. Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for community action in the field of water policy. *Off. J.*
- European Parliament, 2008. DIRECTIVE 2008/105/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 16 December 2008 on environmental quality standards in the field of water policy, amending and subsequently repealing council directives 82/176/EEC, 83/513/EEC, 84/156/EEC, 84/491/EEC. *Off. J. Eur. Communities* L 348, 84–97.
- Felice, B. De, Mondellini, S., Bertazzo, M., Parolini, M., Caloni, F., 2025. Novel miniaturized exposure to evaluate the toxicity of Enniatin B1 on *Daphnia magna*. *Environ. Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.etap.2025.104748>.
- Flynn, R.W., Scott, D.E., Kuhne, W., Soteropoulos, D., Lance, S.L., 2015. Lethal and sublethal measures of chronic copper toxicity in the eastern narrowmouth toad, *Gastrophryne carolinensis*. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 34. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.2835>.
- Ford, J., Hunt, D.A.G.A., Haines, G.E., Lewis, M., Lewis, Y., Green, D.M., 2020. Adrift on a sea of troubles: can amphibians survive in a human-dominated world? *Herpetologica* 76. <https://doi.org/10.1655/0018-0831-76.2.251>.
- Fritz, K.A., Whiles, M.R., 2018. Amphibian-mediated nutrient fluxes across aquatic–terrestrial boundaries of temporary wetlands. *Freshw. Biol.* 63. <https://doi.org/10.1111/fwb.13130>.
- Gaston, K.J., Fuller, R.A., 2008. Commonness, population depletion and conservation biology. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2007.11.001>.
- Godoy, J.L., Vega, J.R., Marchetti, J.L., 2014. Relationships between PCA and PLS-regression. *Chemometr. Intell. Lab. Syst.* 130, 182–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemolab.2013.11.008>.
- Goessens, T., Chen, A., Truong, N.N., De Saeger, S., Vanhaecke, L., De Boevre, M., 2025. Development, validation, and application of an innovative UHPLC-Orbitrap-HRMS method for multi-class analysis of endocrine disruptors in bottled water: Influence of bottle material, water source, and retail price. *Analytica Chimica Acta* 344995.
- Goessens, De Baere, S., De Troyer, N., Deknock, A., Goethals, P., Lens, L., Pasmans, F., Croubels, S., 2020a. Highly sensitive multi-residue analysis of veterinary drugs including coccidiostats and anthelmintics in pond water using UHPLC-MS/MS: application to freshwater ponds in Flanders, Belgium. *Environ. Sci. Process. Impacts* 22, 2117–2131. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0EM00215A>.
- Goessens, T., Huysman, S., De Troyer, N., Deknock, A., Goethals, P., Lens, L., Vanhaecke, L., Croubels, S., 2020b. Multi-class analysis of 46 antimicrobial drug residues in pond water using UHPLC-Orbitrap-HRMS and application to freshwater ponds in Flanders, Belgium. *Talanta* 220, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2020.121326>.
- Goessens, T., Baere, S. De, Troyer, N. De, Deknock, A., Goethals, P., Lens, L., Pasmans, F., Croubels, S., 2021. Multi-residue analysis of 20 mycotoxins including major metabolites and emerging mycotoxins in freshwater using UHPLC-MS/MS and application to freshwater ponds in Flanders, Belgium. *Environ. Res.* 196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.110366>.
- Goessens, T., De Baere, S., Deknock, A., De Troyer, N., Van Leeuwenberg, R., Martel, A., Pasmans, F., Goethals, P., Lens, L., Spanoghe, P., Vanhaecke, L., Croubels, S., 2022. Agricultural contaminants in amphibian breeding ponds: occurrence, risk and correlation with agricultural land use. *Sci. Total Environ.* 806, 150661. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.150661>.
- Griffis-Kyle, K.L., 2005. Ontogenic delays in effects of nitrite exposure on tiger salamanders (*Ambystoma tigrinum tigrinum*) and wood frogs (*Rana sylvatica*). *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 24 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1897/04-452R>.
- Gruchlik, Y., Linge, K., Joll, C., 2018. Removal of organic micropollutants in waste stabilisation ponds: a review. *J. Environ. Manag.* 206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.10.020>.
- Guibal, R., Lissalde, S., Leblanc, J., Cleries, K., Charriau, A., Poulier, G., Mazzella, N., Rebillard, J.-P., Brizard, Y., Guibaud, G., Guibal, R., Lissalde, S., Leblanc, J., Cleries, K., Charriau, A., Poulier, G., Mazzella, N., Rebillard, J.-P., Brizard, Y., Guibaud, G., 2017. Two sampling strategies for an overview of pesticide contamination in an agriculture-extensive headwater stream. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 25. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-017-9883-7>, 2017 2515.
- Hallman, T.A., Brooks, M.L., 2016. Metal-mediated climate susceptibility in a warming world: larval and latent effects on a model amphibian. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 35. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.3337>.
- Hamer, A.J., Barta, B., Bohus, A., Gál, B., Schmera, D., 2021. Roads reduce amphibian abundance in ponds across a fragmented landscape. *Glob. Ecol. Conserv.* 28, e01663. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2021.e01663>.
- Heys, K.A., Shore, R.F., Pereira, M.G., Jones, K.C., Martin, F.L., 2016. Risk assessment of environmental mixture effects. *RSC Adv.* 6 (53), 47844–47857.
- Hoendervangers, P., Goeteyn, L., Rousseau, D.P.L., Cirne, D.G., Spanoghe, P., 2025. Monitoring of pesticides in the processing water and wastewater of vegetable processing companies: sources and treatment challenges. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 13, 119252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2025.119252>.
- Hoffman, G.E., Roussos, P., 2021. Dream: powerful differential expression analysis for repeated measures designs. *Bioinformatics* 37. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btaa687>.
- Huang, M.-Y., Duan, R.-Y., Yin, J.-W., Zhao, Q., Wan, Y.-Y., Liu, Y., 2020. Individual and mixture toxicity of chromium and copper in development, oxidative stress, lipid metabolism and apoptosis of *Bufo gargarizans* embryos. *Aquat. Toxicol.* 229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquatox.2020.105671>.
- Huang, M., Yin, J., Wan, Y., Duan, R., 2025. The influences of pulse exposure versus continuous exposure to cadmium are different: mechanisms elucidated from motor behavior and brain in amphibian larvae. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 299. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2025.118412>.
- Ihle, V., Flach, H., Kaminski, F., Dietmann, P., Pfeffer, S., Kühl, S.J., 2025. Tebuconazole-based fungicide impairs embryonic development of the South African clawed Frog *Xenopus laevis*. *Environ. Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.etap.2025.104708>.
- ISO, I.O. for S., 2007. ISO 10304-1: Water Quality - Determination of Dissolved Anions by Liquid Chromatography of ions—Part 1: Determination of Bromide, Chloride, Fluoride, Nitrate, Nitrite, Phosphate and Sulphate.
- Janin, A., Léna, J.-P., Joly, P., 2011. Beyond occurrence: body condition and stress hormone as integrative indicators of habitat availability and fragmentation in the common toad. *Biol. Conserv.* 144, 1008–1016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2010.12.009>.
- Johnson, J.R., 2018. Methods for handling concentration values below the limit of quantification in PK studies. *PhUSE US Connect* 1–9.
- Jonard, C., Chandelier, A., Eylenbosch, D., Pannecouque, J., Godin, B., Douny, C., Scippo, M.-L., Gofflot, S., Jonard, C., Chandelier, A., Eylenbosch, D., Pannecouque, J., Godin, B., Douny, C., Scippo, M.-L., Gofflot, S., 2025. Multi-mycotoxin analyses by UPLC-MS/MS in wheat: the situation in Belgium in 2023 and 2024. *Foods* 14, 2300–2314. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods14132300>, 2025.
- Kerby, J.L., Storf, A., Kerby, J.L., Storf, A., 2009. Combined effects of atrazine and chlorpyrifos on susceptibility of the tiger salamander to *Ambystoma tigrinum* virus. *EcoHealth* 6. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10393-009-0234-0>, 2009 61.
- Kerby, J.L., Richards-Hrdlicka, K.L., Storf, A., Skelly, D.K., 2010. An examination of amphibian sensitivity to environmental contaminants: are amphibians poor canaries? *Ecol. Lett.* 13, 60–67. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2009.01399.x>.
- Kidd, K.A., Backhaus, T., Brodin, T., Inostroza, P.A., McCallum, E.S., 2024. Environmental risks of pharmaceutical mixtures in aquatic ecosystems: reflections on a decade of research. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 43. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.5726>.
- Kolpin, D.W., Schenzel, J., Meyer, M.T., Phillips, P.J., Hubbard, L.E., Scott, T.-M., Bucheli, T.D., 2014. Mycotoxins: diffuse and point source contributions of natural contaminants of emerging concern to streams. *Sci. Total Environ.* 470–471. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2013.09.062>.
- Lenhardt, P.P., Brihl, C.A., Berger, G., 2015. Temporal coincidence of amphibian migration and pesticide applications on arable fields in spring. *Basic Appl. Ecol.* 16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.baec.2014.10.005>.
- Luedtke, J.A., Chanson, J., Neam, K., Hobin, L., Maciel, A.O., Catenazzi, A., Borzée, A., Hamidy, A., Aowphol, A., Jean, A., Sosa-Bartuano, A., Fong G, A., De Silva, A., Fouquet, A., Angulo, A., Kidov, A.A., Muñoz Saravia, A., Diesmos, A.C., Tominaga, A., et al., 2023. Ongoing declines for the world's amphibians in the face of emerging threats. *Nature* 622, 308–314. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06578-4>.
- Macías, G., Marco, A., Blaustein, A.R., 2007. Combined exposure to ambient UVB radiation and nitrite negatively affects survival of amphibian early life stages. *Sci. Total Environ.* 385. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2007.06.016>.
- Mandrillon, A.-L., Saglio, P., Mandrillon, A.-L., Saglio, P., 2006. Herbicide exposure affects the chemical recognition of a non native predator in common toad tadpoles (*Bufo bufo*). *Chemoecology* 17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00049-006-0354-8>, 2006 171.
- Mann, R.M., Hynes, R.V., Choung, C.B., Wilson, S.P., 2009. Amphibians and agricultural chemicals: review of the risks in a complex environment. *Environ. Pollut.* 157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2009.05.015>.
- Martel, A., Blooi, M., Adriaensens, C., Van Rooij, P., Beukema, W., Fisher, M.C., Farrer, R. A., Schmidt, B.R., Tobler, U., Goka, K., Lips, K.R., K. R., Muletz, C., Zamudio, K. R., Bosch, J., Lötters, S., Wombwell, E., Garner, T. W. J., Cunningham, A. A., Sluijs, A. S.-v. d., Pasmans, F., 2014. Recent introduction of a chytrid fungus endangers Western Palearctic salamanders. *science* 346 (6209), 630–631. doi:10.1126/science.1258268.
- Mathon, B., Ferreol, M., Togola, A., Lardy-Fontan, S., Dabrin, A., Allan, J.J., Staub, P.F., Mazzella, N., Miège, C., 2022. Polar organic chemical integrative samplers as an effective tool for chemical monitoring of surface waters – results from one-year monitoring in France. *Sci. Total Environ.* 824. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.153549>.

- Merrington, G., Peters, A., Schlegel, C.E., 2016. Accounting for metal bioavailability in assessing water quality: a step change? *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 35 (2), 257–265.
- Munkhsul, E., Murayama, T., Fukushi, K., Nishikizawa, S., Gankhurel, B., Batbold, T., Ochir, A., 2024. Heavy metal concentrations and water quality assessment of different types of drinking water wells in the Erdenet Cu–Mo mining area. *Discover Environment* 2 (1), 12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44274-024-00037-1>.
- Navarro, I., Torre, A. de la, Sanz, P., Abrantes, N., Campos, I., Alaoui, A., Christ, F., Alcon, F., Contreras, J., Glavan, M., Pasković, I., Pasković, M.P., Nørgaard, T., Mandrioli, D., Sgargi, D., Hofman, J., Aparicio, V., Baldi, I., Bureau, M., et al., 2024. Assessing pesticide residues occurrence and risks in water systems: a Pan-European and Argentina perspective. *Water Res.* 254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2024.121419>.
- Nolan, N., Hayward, M.W., Klop-Toker, K., Mahony, M., Lemckert, F., Callen, A., 2023. Complex organisms must deal with complex threats: how does amphibian conservation deal with biphasic life cycles? *Animal* 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani13101634>, 2023, Page 1634 13.
- Oksanen, J., Blanchet, F., Kindt, R., Legendre, P., Minchin, P., O'Hara, R., Solymos, P., Stevens, M., Szoecs, G., Simpson, G., E Barbour, M., Bedward, M., Bolker, B., Borcard, D., Carvalho, G., Chirico, M., De Caceres, M., Durand, S.W.H., Evangelista H Friendly, M., Furneaux, B., Hannigan, G., Hill, M., Lahti, L., McGlenn, D., Ouellette, M., F. R., Ribeiro Cunha, E., Stier, A., Ter Braak, C., Weedon, J., Borman, T., S. T., 2025. Vegan: community ecology package. R package version 2.6-10. <https://doi.org/10.1007/jom.000000000001647>.
- Ortiz, M.E., Marco, A., Saiz, N., Lizana, M., Ortiz, M.E., Marco, A., Saiz, N., Lizana, M., 2004. Impact of ammonium nitrate on growth and survival of six European amphibians. *Arch. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.* 47. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00244-004-2296-x>, 2004 472.
- Peluso, J., Chehda, A.M., Olivelli, M.S., Ivanic, F.M., Coll, C.S.P., Gonzalez, F., Valenzuela, L., Rojas, D., Cristos, D., Butler, M., Candal, R.J., Aronzon, C.M., 2023. Metals, pesticides, and emerging contaminants on water bodies from agricultural areas and the effects on a native amphibian. *Environ. Res.* 226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.115692>.
- Petrovan, S.O., Moor, H., Schmidt, B.R., Petrovan, S.O., Moor, H., Schmidt, B.R., 2025. Increasingly uncommon common toads: multidecadal, ongoing abundance decline of a widespread amphibian despite volunteer conservation action. *Biodivers. Conserv.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-025-03150-6>, 2025.
- Pochini, K.M., Hoverman, J.T., 2017. Reciprocal effects of pesticides and pathogens on amphibian hosts: the importance of exposure order and timing. *Environ. Pollut.* 221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2016.11.086>.
- Quiroga, L.B., Gordillo, L.F., Aragon-Traverso, J.H., Iribas, F.J., Sanabria, E.A., 2024. Thermal sensitivity of *Rhinella arenarum* tadpole at low concentrations of dimethoate pesticides. *Comp. Biochem. Physiol., Part C: Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbpc.2024.109884>.
- Reading, C.J., Jofré, G.M., 2021. Declining common toad body size correlated with climate warming. *Biol. J. Linn. Soc.* 134, 577–586. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biolinnean/blas101>.
- Relyea, R.A., 2003. Predator cues and pesticides: a double dose of danger for amphibians. *Ecol. Appl.* 13. <https://doi.org/10.1890/02-5298>.
- Ribeiro, A.R., Maia, A., Santos, M., Tiritan, M.E., Ribeiro, C.M.R., Ribeiro, A.R., Maia, A., Santos, M., Tiritan, M.E., Ribeiro, C.M.R., 2015. Occurrence of natural contaminants of emerging concern in the Douro River Estuary, Portugal. *Arch. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.* 70. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00244-015-0212-1>, 2015 702.
- Ritchie, M.E., Phipson, B., Wu, D., Hu, Y., Law, C.W., Shi, W., Smyth, G.K., 2015. Limma powers differential expression analyses for RNA-seq and microarray studies. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 43. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkv007>.
- Rohr, J.R., Schotthoefer, A.M., Raffel, T.R., Carrick, H.J., Halstead, N., Hoverman, J.T., Johnson, C.M., Johnson, L.B., Lieske, C., Piwoni, M.D., Schoff, P.K., Beasley, V.R., Rohr, J.R., Schotthoefer, A.M., Raffel, T.R., Carrick, H.J., Halstead, N., Hoverman, J. T., Johnson, C.M., et al., 2008. Agrochemicals increase trematode infections in a declining amphibian species. *Nature* 455. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature07281>, 2008 4557217.
- Salazar, R.D., Montgomery, R.A., Thresher, S.E., Macdonald, D.W., 2016. Mapping the relative probability of common toad occurrence in terrestrial lowland farm habitat in the United Kingdom. *PLoS One* 11, e0148269. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0148269>.
- Schenzel, J., Hungerbühler, K., Bucheli, T.D., 2012. Mycotoxins in the environment: II. Occurrence and origin in Swiss River waters. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es301558>.
- Schreiner, V.C., Szöcs, E., Bhowmik, A.K., Vijver, M.G., Schäfer, R.B., 2016. Pesticide mixtures in streams of several European countries and the USA. *Sci. Total Environ.* 573, 680–689. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.08.163>.
- Schymanski, E.L., Jeon, J., Gulde, R., Fenner, K., Ruff, M., Singer, H.P., Hollender, J., 2014. Identifying small molecules via high resolution mass spectrometry: communicating confidence. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es5002105>.
- Sievers, M., Hale, R., Swearer, S.E., Parris, K.M., 2018. Contaminant mixtures interact to impair predator-avoidance behaviours and survival in a larval amphibian. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2018.06.028>.
- Slaby, S., Catteau, A., Cor, F. Le, Cant, A., Dufour, V., Iurétig, A., Turies, C., Palluel, O., Bado-Nilles, A., Bonnard, M., Cardoso, O., Dauchy, X., Porcher, J.-M., Banas, D., 2023. Chemical occurrence of pesticides and transformation products in two small lentic waterbodies at the head of agricultural watersheds and biological responses in caged *Gasterosteus aculeatus*. *Sci. Total Environ.* 904. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.166326>.
- Smalling, K.L., Reeves, R., Muths, E., Vandever, M., Battaglin, W.A., Hladik, M.L., Pierce, C.L., 2015. Pesticide concentrations in frog tissue and wetland habitats in a landscape dominated by agriculture. *Sci. Total Environ.* 502, 80–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCITOTENV.2014.08.114>.
- Smith, G.R., Temple, K.G., Dingfelder, H.A., Vaala, D.A., Smith, G.R., Temple, K.G., Dingfelder, H.A., Vaala, D.A., 2005. Effects of nitrate on the interactions of the tadpoles of two ranids (*Rana clamitans* and *R. catesbeiana*). *Aquat. Ecol.* 40. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10452-005-9015-1>, 2005 401.
- Smith, M.R., Uppal, K., Walker, D.I., Utell, M.J., Hopke, P.K., Mallon, T.M., Krahl, P.L., Rohrbeck, P., Go, Y.-M., Jones, D.P., 2019. Environmental chemicals altered in association with deployment for high risk areas. *J. Occup. Environ. Med.* 61. <https://doi.org/10.1097/JOM.0000000000001647>.
- Stegen, G., Pasmans, F., Schmidt, B.R., Rouffier, L.O., Van Praet, S., Schaub, M., Canessa, S., Laudelout, A., Kinet, T., Adriaenssens, C., Haesebrouck, F., Bert, W., Bossuyt, F., Martel, A., Stegen, G., Pasmans, F., Schmidt, B.R., Rouffier, L.O., Van Praet, S., Martel, A., 2017. Drivers of salamander extirpation mediated by *Batrachochytrium* salamandrivorans. *Nature* 544 (7650), 353–356. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature22059>.
- Taylor, N.S., Sadowski, J., Schuster, H.S., Weyers, A., Weltje, L., 2024. Occurrence of common frog (*Rana temporaria*) and common toad (*Bufo bufo*) adults and metamorphs in agricultural fields in Germany: potential for exposure to plant protection products. *Integrated Environ. Assess. Manag.* 20. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ieam.4952>.
- Tsaturyan, A., Sahakyan, L., Hayrapetyan, L., Minasyan, E., Chakhoyan, A., Hayrapetyan, S., Saghyan, A., 2024. Ion-chromatographic determination of common anions in drinking water in some regions of the Republic of Armenia. *Pharmacia*(71) 1–9.
- Ulrich, U., Hörmann, G., Unger, M., Pfannerstill, M., Steinmann, F., Fohrer, N., 2018. Lentic small water bodies: variability of pesticide transport and transformation patterns. *Sci. Total Environ.* 618. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.11.032>.
- Veronez, A.C. da S., Salla, R.V., Baroni, V.D., Barcarolli, I.F., Bianchini, A., Martinez, C. B., dos, R., Chippari-Gomes, A.R., 2016. Genetic and biochemical effects induced by iron ore, Fe and Mn exposure in tadpoles of the bullfrog *Lithobates catesbeianus*. *Aquat. Toxicol.* 174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquatox.2016.02.011>.
- Vlarem, I.I., 1995. Besluit van de Vlaamse regering houdende algemene en sectorale bepalingen inzake milieuhygiëne (Vlarem II). In: Bijlage 2.3.1. Basismilieukwaliteitsnormen Voor Oppervlaktewater, Belgisch Staatsblad.
- WAC, 2025. Ministerieel Besluit Tot goedkeuring van het compendium voor de monsterneming, meting en analyse van water (WAC) en tot wijziging van bijlage 4.2.5.2 bij het besluit van de Vlaamse Regering van 1 juni 1995 houdende algemene en sectorale bepalingen inzake.
- Wang, Y., Yang, G., Dai, D., Xu, Z., Cai, L., Wang, Q., Yu, Y., 2017. Individual and mixture effects of five agricultural pesticides on zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) larvae. *Environ. Sci. Pol.* 24, 4528–4536. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-016-8205-9>.
- Warsneski, D., Rutkoski, C.F., Israel, N.G., Gonçalves, G.H.P., Lã, L., Guerreiro, F., Giasson, L.O.M., Albuquerque, C.A.C. de, Hasckel, R.P., Silva, E.B. da, Alves, T.C., Almeida, E.A. de, 2024. Fungicides from rice cultivation (tebuconazole and azoxystrobin) alters biochemical and histological markers of hammetoad tadpoles (*Boana faber*). *Environ. Pollut.* 341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2023.122900>.
- Wickham, H., 2016. ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis. Springer-Verlag, New York.
- Willson, J.D., Hopkins, W.A., Bergeron, C.M., Todd, B.D., 2012. Making leaps in amphibian ecotoxicology: translating individual-level effects of contaminants to population viability. *Ecol. Appl.* 22 (6). <https://doi.org/10.1890/11-0915.1>.
- Wood, L., Welch, A.M., 2015. Assessment of interactive effects of elevated salinity and three pesticides on life history and behavior of southern toad (*Anaxyrus terrestris*) tadpoles. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 34. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.2861>.
- Yu, M., Tu, P., Dolios, G., Dassanayake, P.S., Volk, H., Newschaffer, C., Fallin, M.D., Croen, L., Lyall, K., Schmidt, R., Hertz-Picciotto, I., Austin, C., Arora, M., Petrick, L. M., 2021. Tooth biomarkers to characterize the temporal dynamics of the fetal and early-life exposome. *Environ. Int.* 157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106849>.
- Zhu, G., Wen, Y., Cao, K., He, S., Wang, T., 2024. A review of common statistical methods for dealing with multiple pollutant mixtures and multiple exposures. *Front. Public Health* 12, 1377685.